

Stereochemistry of Michael Addition. Part I. Adduct of Nitromethane and 1-Acetylcyclohexene

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The adduct of nitromethane and 1-acetylcyclohexene has been proved to be a *cis* compound by synthetical experiments.

It has been observed that frequently, if not generally, Michael additions to 1-acetylcyclohexene (I) afford *trans* products¹. The *trans* addition has been mostly inferred from the fact that the dicyclic compounds, obtained by a further internal condensation of the initial adduct, are *trans* fused. These condensations are, however, effected in basic medium, which allows equilibration, and isolation of a more stable *trans* dicyclic isomer cannot be taken as a conclusive evidence for the stereochemistry of the initial adduct.

In the present investigation the adduct (II) of nitromethane and 1-acetylcyclohexene² has been shown to have *cis* configuration. The nitro-ketone (II) was reduced by tin and hydrochloric acid to 1-methyloctahydroisoindole(V). The same pyrrolidine had also been obtained by catalytic hydrogenation. Methylation of this amine(V) with formic acid and formaldehyde gave *N*-methyl-1-methyloctahydroisoindole (VI), which on the Hofmann degradation afforded the known *cis*-2-dimethylaminomethyl-1-vinylcyclohexane (VII). The Hofmann degradation was expected to take the observed direction as only the methyl hydrogens can acquire a configuration which is *trans* and *co-planar* with the breaking C-N bond (VIII). Further, according to the Hofmann rule also, the methyl hydrogens should be attacked in preference to ring-juncture tertiary hydrogens³.

An earlier attempt to establish the stereochemistry of the adduct (II) by conversion to the known *cis*-2-dimethylamino-1-ethylcyclohexane was unsuccessful. The amino-alcohol (IV), obtained by inverse lithium aluminium hydride reduction, followed by methylation, failed to yield a tosylate which was required for unambiguous replacement of the hydroxy group. Inverse lithium aluminium hydride addition is suitable for reducing nitro-ketones to pharmacologically important amino-alcohols as the competing ring closure is minimum under these conditions.

Models show that *cis*-1-acetyl-2-nitromethylcyclohexane (II) should be less stable than its *trans* isomer. Its formation is probably a result of kinetic control of the addition, the approach of a proton to the intermediate anion (IX) being easier from the side opposite to the two axial hydrogen atoms (cf. the formation of less stable ketone in ketonisation of

1. Organic reactions, Vol. 10, p. 201, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1959.

2. Kessar and Kloetzel, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 1314.

3. cf. Jewers and McKenna, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2209.

the enol of 1-benzoyl-2-phenylcyclohexanone.)⁴ The initially formed *cis* product may not be isomerising due to the large excess of acidic nitromethane used in the addition. Isomerisation evidently does not take place in the reduction step also because the thermodynamically unstable *cis* isomer of 1-methyloctahydroisindole is obtained. (The relative stability of perhydroisindole isomers should be similar to that of hydrindanes⁵).

*EXPERIMENTAL

1-Acetyl-2-nitromethylcyclohexane (II).—1-Acetylcyclohexene (II) was prepared from 1-acetylcyclohexene and nitromethane (10 *M*) according to the method of Kessar and Kloetzel². The fraction boiling at 105-107°/1.5mm was shown to be stereochemically pure, the I. R. spectra of an initial and final cut being superimposable.

*Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford, and by Mr. B. N. Anand, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh.

4. Zimmerman, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 549.

5. Allinger and Coke, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 2553.

1-(2-Aminomethylcyclohexyl)-ethanol (III).—To a stirred solution of (II) (7g. in 100 ml dry ether) was added during 2 hours a slurry of LiAlH_4 (4g. in 100 ml dry ether). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hours and then decomposed by dropwise addition of water (9 ml) while the stirring was continued. The precipitated solid was removed and thoroughly extracted with ether (100 ml). The combined ethereal layer was washed with water and dried. The solvent was removed and the residue fractionated to collect a colorless liquid (3.9 g.), b.p. 110-15°/3 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4916. (Found: C, 68.60; H, 12.20; N, 8.75. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}$ requires C, 68.73; H, 12.17; N, 8.90%).

1-(2-Dimethylaminomethylcyclohexyl)-ethanol (IV).—A mixture of (III) (2.5 g.), formic acid (4 ml, 98%), and formaldehyde (5 ml, 40%) was heated on a steam bath for 7 hours. The excess of aldehyde and of acid were distilled under reduced pressure and the solid residue was refluxed with 15% NaOH solution (30 ml) for 4 hours. The organic material was taken in ether, washed with water, and dried. The solvent was removed and the residue distilled to collect a colorless oil (1.9 g.), b.p. 106-108°/7 mm., n_D^{25} 1.4742. (Found: N, 7.45. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}\text{ON}$ requires N, 7.57%).

Attempted Tosylation of 1-(2-Dimethylaminomethylcyclohexyl)-ethanol.—A solution of (IV) (1 g.) and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (4 g.) in minimum quantity of dry pyridine was heated for 10 minutes on a steam bath and allowed to stand overnight. When it was diluted with excess of water, no precipitate or oil was obtained. The solution was made alkaline and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed free of pyridine, dried, and the solvent evaporated. No pure substance could be isolated from the small oily residue. Variations in temperature and time of the reaction gave equally disappointing results⁶.

1-Methyloctahydroisoindole (V).—A mixture of compound (II) (5 g.), tin metal (17g.), and HCl (conc., 60ml) was heated for 2 hours on a steam bath and then refluxed for 8 hours in an oil bath. It was cooled and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was made alkaline with NaOH and steam-distilled to collect 500 ml of the distillate which was acidified with HCl and evaporated to dryness. The residue was made alkaline with NaOH and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water, dried, and the solvent removed. The residue on fractionation gave a colorless oil (2.3 g.), b.p. 75-80°/5mm. It gave a picrate from ether solution which on crystallisation from benzene afforded yellow needles, m.p. 134-35°. (Found: C, 49.05; H, 5.42; N, 15.20. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_7\text{N}_4$ requires C, 48.90; H, 5.47; N, 15.21%). No depression in m.p. on admixture with the picrate of the pyrrolidine obtained by hydrogenation (platinum) of the nitro-ketone (II) according to Kessar and Kloetzel⁴ was observed.

N-Methyl-1-methyloctahydroisoindole (VI).—A mixture of (V) (2.9 g.), formic acid (12.5 ml, 98%) and formaldehyde (12.5 ml, 40%) was heated on a steam bath for 6 hours. From the yellow solution obtained, 20 ml liquid was distilled under reduced pressure, the residue was made alkaline with NaOH solution (conc.), and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water, dried, and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation gave a colorless oil (2.1 g.) b.p. 80-85°/5 mm. The picrate on crystallisation from ethanol afforded yellow needles, m.p. 189-91°. (Found: N, 14.52. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_7\text{N}_4$ requires N, 14.66%).

Hofmann Degradation of N-Methyl-1-methyloctahydroisoindole (VI).—A solution of the compound (VI) (2.1 g.) and methyl iodide (60 ml) in ether (20 ml) was allowed to stand overnight. The precipitated methiodide was filtered and dissolved in distilled water (15 ml). To this was added silver oxide, freshly prepared from silver nitrate (5 g.) and NaOH (1.2 g.). The mixture was shaken in dark for 8 hours. The silver salt was filtered and the clear solution concentrated at 45-60° under a pressure of 40 mm. The bath temperature was then raised to 120-40° to collect a colorless liquid (0.95 g.), b.p. 92-95°/40 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4630; King and Booth⁷ recorded n_D^{20} 1.4679.

The methiodide crystallised from acetone, m.p. 252-254° (King and Booth⁷ recorded m.p. 253-54°).

Picrate crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 110-11.5°; (King and Booth⁷ recorded m.p. 111-13°). (Found: N, 14.37. C₇H₂₄O₇N₄ requires N, 14.14%).

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7. King and Booth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3798.